

IMAGE CAPTION GENERATION USING CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK AND LONG SHORT-TERM MEMORY

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Abstract— Making descriptive textual captions for images is known as image captioning, and it is an important task in computer vision and natural language processing. This paper provides a method combining Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). CNNs are used to extract high-level features from input images, while LSTM networks are used to create captions that make sense and are relevant to the context based on the features extracted. Flickr8K dataset is used for training and obtained a BLEU-1 score of 0.4271. Through a collaborative training procedure, the suggested model gains the ability to correlate visual elements with related textual descriptions. The CNN-LSTM architecture can outperform the conventional methods by creating meaningful and accurate visual descriptions.

Keywords—VGG16, CNN, RNN, Tensorflow, LSTM, BLEU Score

I. INTRODUCTION

A fascinating nexus between natural language processing and computer vision is represented by image captioning, which enables computers to annotate photographs using language similar to that of humans. In order to understand image and produce meaningful captions that are similar to how people see and describe visual content, this seminar paper explores the field of image captioning. It does this by using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). The fundamental working principle of image captioning is the synergy between CNNs and RNNs. If CNNs are the "eye" of the computer, then RNNs are the "mouth," converting these visual traits into comprehensible textual descriptions. Additionally, the research uses LSTM architectures—a type of deep learning technique—to train models that can provide captions for photos in an efficient manner.

A. CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are the predominant type of neural network employed for addressing image processing tasks. These networks, which operate in a feed-forward manner, are designed with a grid-like topology, making them well-suited for analyzing visual data, such as images. Convolutional neural networks can be used in projects involving natural language processing as well image recognition. Another name of CNN is ConvNet. These

networks allow computer to identify the important elements in an image. These key elements are translated into special set of numbers that the computer understands. These numbers are called 'Vector Embeddings'.

As illustrated in Figure 1, a convolutional neural network consists of four key layers: the pooling layer, the fully connected layer, the ReLU layer, and the convolution layer. Extracting features from the image is the first step. Multiple filters work together to perform the convolution action in a convolution layer. Higher-level features are progressively recovered from the input image as it moves through the convolutional layers, capturing increasingly intricate patterns and structures. ReLU, short for Rectified Linear Unit, is a common term in neural networks. Following this, the retrieved feature maps are directed to a ReLU layer. ReLU operates element-wise, setting all negative pixels to 0, thereby introducing non-linearity to the network. Consequently, the output is a rectified feature map. A method known as pooling, used for downsampling, reduces the dimensionality of the feature map. This involves passing the corrected feature map through a pooling layer to generate the pooled feature map. The image's edges, corners, body, feathers, eyes, and beak are among the elements that the pooling layer recognizes using a variety of filters.

Fig 1

A Recurrent Neural Network(RNN) is a type of artificial neural network. These takes vector embedding from CNN and combines them with meaningful words. The RNN begins building sentences one word at a time.

We're ready to bring our captions to life once we have our image features. Our algorithm learns from the LSTM model to produce insightful descriptions for our image.

Fig 2

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Zhang H., et al. [1] proposed a unique approach to image caption synthesis employing contextual information fusion with Bi-LSTM-s. They achieved this by capturing past and future information using a Bi-directional Long Short-Term Memory (Bi-LSTM) structure, which allowed for the prediction of image content based on contextual cues. To extract semantic information from visual inputs, they specifically used a forward LSTM decoder (F-LSTM) and a backward LSTM decoder (B-LSTM). Abbreviations and Acronyms. The model's performance was 9.7% better than the original LSTM model, indicating that it is capable of producing insightful image captions. However, it adds computational complexity that may result in longer training times and more resources being needed.

Hossain MD Z., et al. [2] address the connection of computer vision and natural language processing by presenting a novel method for producing textual descriptions of images. The authors uses both synthetic and real data for testing and training. Attention-based generative adversarial networks (GANs) provide an economical substitute for gathering massive amounts of manually annotated data when it comes to creating synthetic visuals from text. Because this method cuts down on the time and resources needed to create datasets, it's especially advantageous for applications with little funding. But model trained on synthetic data find it difficult to generalize well to real-world circumstances if the distribution of training data is not the same. The model's capacity to produce precise and contextually appropriate descriptions for unseen images may be impacted by this disparity between artificial and actual visuals.

Hinz T., et al. [3] proposes conditional Generative Adversarial Networks (cGANs) that have emerged as a prominent framework for generating images conditioned on textual inputs. Attention mechanisms have been integrated to improve the alignment between text and images by dynamically focusing on relevant parts of the input. Object-level modeling techniques have enabled the generation of images with finer details and richer semantics by explicitly modeling individual objects within images. Additionally, the exploration of synthetic data generation and cross-domain image generation has expanded the applicability of text-to-image models, leading to improved performance and generalization capabilities. By explicitly modeling individual objects in images, the suggested model produces realistic-looking images that closely match written descriptions. A

disadvantage is that there aren't many metrics available to measure how well generated images match their captions, making it difficult to evaluate text-to-image models quantitatively.

Fatima N.S., et al. [4] proposes the Summarization of Text and Image Captioning in Information Retrieval Using Deep Learning Techniques, an innovative approach based on deep learning for text summarization and information retrieval. Three primary processes are included in the suggested model: the creation of templates using a deep belief network (DBN), text summarization using the DBN model, and information retrieval using bidirectional long short-term memory (BiLSTM). The usefulness of the proposed methodology is demonstrated by the experimental findings, which show improved performance in terms of precision, recall, F-score, and BLEU scores when compared to existing methods. Additionally, real-time applications or environments with limited resources may encounter difficulties due to the computational complexity of deep learning models such as DBN and BiLSTM.

Ueda A., et al. [5] proposes an approach to maximize the use of various modalities within an image in order to improve text-based image captioning (TextCaps) task performance. The authors do this by enhancing the image and optical character recognition (OCR) language properties using pre-trained CLIP models. The representation of the picture modality is strengthened by adding two more attention models to the transformer design that incorporates these aspects. To successfully capture the link between recognized objects and linguistic elements in the picture, the multimodal transformer model incorporates four image-related modalities: CLIP features, image features, OCR text. Through the incorporation of an additional encoding module dedicated to the linguistic aspect of OCR tokens, enhancements are made to OCR text information. This enhancement aids the model in more effectively capturing textual components within the image. Drawback: Although the method outperforms baseline techniques, more study may be required to solve certain issues with handling non-Latin characters or different languages in OCR recognition, particularly for languages other than English.

Ramos R., et al. [6] proposes captioning remote sensing images, which entails creating short written descriptions for aerial images. This paper explores a different method for caption generation using continuous outputs instead of discrete word tokens. The proposed method strives to improve the capture of overall semantic similarity between captions and images. Experimental results on UCM and RSICD datasets show that the continuous output framework outperforms the standard discrete output approach, demonstrating competitiveness against state-of-the-art models. Continuous outputs improve the global semantic similarity between captions and images. But the attention mechanism used in the model is simplistic and may not fully capture the relevance of different image regions.

Saba T., et al. [7] proposes a fully trained generative adversarial network (GAN) to address the challenge of text-to-face generation. Unlike existing approaches that rely on

partially trained GANs, this method simultaneously trains both the text encoder and the image decoder within the GAN framework. By training both the text encoder and image decoder simultaneously, the proposed method leverages the complementary relationship between text and image representations, resulting in more accurate and realistic image synthesis. However, the model's performance in generating images outside the scope of the provided dataset may be suboptimal.

Bae J.W., et al. [8] proposed a model incorporates a POS guidance module to enhance lexical diversity in image captions. This module controls the intensity of images and word sequences based on predicted POS guidance, enabling richer expression in generated sentences. The image captioning model combines POS information with output vectors from a Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (Bi-LSTM) network using a multimodal layer. By leveraging the POS guidance module, the proposed model generates captions with greater lexical diversity compared to existing approaches. This enriches the expressiveness and variety of the generated sentences. But this model adds complexity to the model architecture, potentially increasing computational requirements during training and inference.

III. METHOD OF IMPLEMENTATION

A. Import necessary modules

The first step was to import basic libraries like pickle, numpy, matplotlib and PIL. Also import the deep learning framework tensorflow.

B. Image Features Extraction

Each image is processed where image pixels are converted to numpy array using 'img_to_array'. The preprocessed is passed through the model and extract the image features. The VGG16 model was chosen as the pre-trained model for this project because of its ability in extracting both basic and complicated characteristics from images. The function loads the VGG16 model that has already been trained, eliminates the final layer of classification, and outputs a summary of the updated model. The extracted image features are saved to a pickle file named 'img_features.pkl' using pickle.dump.

```
# We are going to use pretrained vgg model
# Load the vgg16 model
model = VGG16()

# Restructuring the model to remove the last classification layer, this
model = Model(inputs=model.inputs, outputs=model.layers[-2].output)

# Printing the model summary
print(model.summary())
```

Fig 3

C. Caption Loading and Preprocessing

This step involves cleaning the captions by converting them to lowercase, remove non-alphabetical characters, extra spaces and adding the start and end tokens. After preprocessing concatenate all preprocessed captions from the

dataset into a single list for further processing. The text is then tokenized that is converting text into numerical values or tokens. There are over 40455 captions for 8091 images.

D. Train Test Split

Next, the data is divided into testing and training sets. The first 90% of image IDs are assigned to the training set('train') and 10% to the test set('test').

E. LSTM Model Training

Tokenized captions and image characteristics retrieved by a pre-trained VGG16 model are fed into the LSTM model. It then uses bidirectional LSTM layers to encode image characteristics and caption sequences independently, allowing it to collect context from the past and the future. The attention mechanism helps the model to concentrate on the most useful portions of the input by determining how relevant each caption section is to the features of the image. The LSTM model is then trained for specified number of epochs. The model is then saved using model.save.

```
# Save the model
model.save(OUTPUT_DIR+'mymodel.h5')
```

Fig 4

F. Caption Generation

This creates captions for images by using the learned LSTM model. The trained model is used by the predict_caption function to create a caption for the supplied image features. It accepts as inputs the model, image features, tokenizer, and maximum caption length.

G. Prediction and evaluation

1. Now we can predict the caption using generate_caption function. This function extracts the image ID from the image name and open using 'Image.open()' function. It then predicts the actual captions for the image using 'predict_caption()' function.

The predicted captions are evaluated using BLEU (Bilingual Evaluation Understudy). The NLTK package contains a function called corpus_bleu that calculates BLEU scores. A higher score denotes better agreement between the expected and real captions. The BLEU score runs from 0 to 1. BLEU-1 in this instance is 0.379877, whereas BLEU-2 is 0.167031, showing how well the produced captions compare to the actual data.

TABLE 1 : BLEU SCORE EVALUATION

Model	BLEU SCORE EVALUATION		
	BLEU-1	BLEU-2	BLEU-4
CNN	0.427171	0.181836	0.046367

Fig 5

IV. RESULT

The image captioning project is deployed on Streamlit app. This Streamlit app allows users to upload an image, after which it generates a caption for the image using pre-trained LSTM model. By deploying it in streamlit, image captioning can be easily accessible through a web interface.

Image Caption Generator

Upload an image, and this app will generate a caption for it using a trained LSTM model.

Choose an image

Fig 6

Uploaded Image

Uploaded Image

Generated Caption

" man in aerodynamic gear riding bicycle down road around sharp curve "

Fig 7

V. CONCLUSION

2.

In this project, we used Streamlit to launch the Image Caption Generator that we created using deep learning algorithms. The project's objective was to develop an interactive, user-friendly application that could produce insightful descriptions for images that users uploaded. The project obtained a BLEU score of 0.427171 which indicates the precision of the machine-generated captions compared to the reference captions

In conclusion, Streamlit's Image Caption Generator effectively combines web development and machine learning technology, offering a useful tool for instantly creating insightful explanations for images.

VI. REFERENCES

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